

What does the future hold for Biodiversity Hotspots? A systematic map exploring spatial patterns and knowledge gaps & clusters of ecological range shifts in plants

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January 12, 2022 (updated March 2, 2022)

Summary

Research into ecological range shift has increased exponentially in recent years as ecologists attempt to understand responses to global change drivers. To our knowledge, we produced one of the first global systematic maps investigating terrestrial plant range shift studies. After screening >7,000 articles, we used “EviAtlas” to synthesise 294 studies into an open-source web map database. The results highlight Sub-Saharan Africa and Central America as understudied Hotspot regions. Studies are predominantly predictive in nature, highlighting difficulties in establishing long-term monitoring to measure empirical range shift on the ground. Moreover, most studies opt for correlative species distribution modelling techniques, rather than process-based (mechanistic) models. The application of most studies is to supply evidence on the impacts of climate change, for conservation and invasion management purposes. Adopting a research strategy that emphasises use of demographic, physiological, and species -or- genera-specific data is paramount for constructing models capable of accurately predicting future range shift.

KEYWORDS: systematic map, range shift, species distributions, climate change, plants

1. Introduction

The last thirty years of range shift research have led to an accumulation of studies, suggesting species are likely to alter their distributions globally in response to climate change (Klausmeyer and Shaw, 2009, Kuhn et al., 2016, Malcolm et al., 2006, Wróblewska and Mirski, 2018). Anthropogenic change is heightening the effects of global change at local levels, resulting in multiple taxa being forced from their original habitats, with less opportunities to successfully adapt due to fragmentation and other alterations to the landscape mosaic. Many studies have modelled ways in which plants may respond to climatic change via range shifts, however, most have tended to focus on climate-only, correlative models, due to time or cost constraints. Many have tended to omit factors such as local-level changes in land-use, and land cover into model parameterisation.

1.1. Objective

Conduct a global systematic map (review) to synthesise plant range shift studies to date, and identify knowledge and geographical clusters and gaps to inform direction of ongoing ecological shift research on terrestrial plant species globally.

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2. Methods

Generally, systematic maps are similar to systematic reviews, with a focus on visual synthesis of data in question rather than a traditional scoping review (Evidence, 2013). We followed the standard systematic mapping methods of (James et al., 2016) to collate relevant studies, published within the last 30 years, that have empirically measured or predictively modelled terrestrial plant species range shifts.

2.1. Article searching and database queries

The search for relevant articles was undertaken using multiple databases including Scopus, ISI Web of Knowledge, and Science Direct to gather as wider reach as possible. Search terms were trialled and analysed the pilot study to interpret which terms returned higher numbers of search results to encompass all possible studies relating to range shift. The pilot study identified papers from multiple language sources, therefore each database query was set to collate results in all languages.

2.2. Screening

Duplicate articles were removed prior to blind screening of remaining range shift studies, assessed for relevance to the following criteria using MetaGear R package (Lajeunesse, 2016):

- i. Studies that assessed range shift on flora (studies that included fauna and flora were removed).
- ii. Articles that were terrestrial-only (aquatic/salt-water species, and non-terrestrial flora studies were removed. This also excluded Thallophyta plant subgroup).
- iii. Studies published between 1990-2020 in peer-reviewed journals (any articles published before 1990 were removed. Articles published in 2021 were monitored but not included as there was not a full year of data at the time of analysis).
- iv. Studies that predicted future range shift (any studies whose sole focus was researching past shifting were excluded).
- v. Articles that physically measure or predict range shift (methodological or review papers were removed).

2.3. Coding categorisation and full text reading

Articles that passed screening were then "coded" to record the nature of each study and techniques used including scale, geographical location, plant major group, number of species, software, modelling parameters, and range shift measurements (Table 1).

2.4. Creation of Systematic Map

We uploaded the coded study data to an open source, web-based software "EviAtlas" to display the final results as an interactive web map (Haddaway et al., 2019). Contextual and geographical analysis took place in ArcGIS Pro to study trends in the data in more depth. This included geostatistical analysis to study the spatial patterns across the different codes measured (Getis and Ord, 1992).

3. Results

The global heatmap highlighted that 74% of all studies took place north of the Equator, and only 28% of studies fell within a terrestrial Biodiversity Hotspot (Figure 1). Geographical gaps in range shift studies are visible in Central America and Sub-Saharan Africa (Figure 1). Most studies (86%) used predictive-only approaches to forecast future range shifts on their chosen plant species, and 14% utilised empirical data to support predictions (Figure 2). Publications increased exponentially between 2007 and 2020 (Figure 3). Studies were published in 113 different journals, and two books.

4. Discussion

To our knowledge, this was the first systematic map exploring the ‘how, where and why’ of terrestrial plant range shifting globally, presented as geographical and knowledge clusters and gaps. When mapped out, geographical clusters (e.g., the many regions of the world where this type of research has focused over the last 30 years) also highlight the inequalities of where research has not been a focus to date. Knowledge clusters (e.g., the heavy reliance on correlative modelling approaches) present an opportunity to diversify from these statistical methods, in favour of a more “bottom-up”, process-based methods to achieve a greater representation of real-world change drivers within model predictions.

5. Figures and Tables

Figure 1 A global systematic map of terrestrial plant range shift studies (blue dots) across a thirty-year period (1990-2020) visualised in ArcGIS Pro using density heatmap overlaid with global Biodiversity Hotspots (burnt red). Biodiversity Hotspots data source: <https://data.globalforestwatch.org/>. Just 28% of all studies occur within a designated terrestrial Biodiversity Hotspot. Of those, 65% predicted an overall contraction in species ranges.

Figure 2 A descriptive plot describing the systematic map study type (empirical or predictive) produced in EviAtlas. “Empirical” refers to studies that include field collected data of existing shifts to predict future range shift, and predictive reference studies that use predictive methods only.

Figure 3 A descriptive plot describing an exponential increase in range shift studies published from 1990-2020 (figure produced in EviAtlas).

Table 1 Summary and description of all systematic map coding categories

Systematic Coding	Map	Code description / examples
Standard review identification	systematic codes -	Source Journal, Publication Year, Language Origin, Access Type (e.g., open access), Article Type (e.g., primary, secondary)
Standard map codes - visual	systematic codes -	Scale (Local, Regional e.g., more than one county/district, National (countrywide), International (spanning more than 1 country)) Geography (North America, Central America, South America, The Caribbean, EU, Eastern Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa, Middle East, Asia, Oceania, Antarctica, Global) Latitude/Longitude (precision depending on scale/resolution of study) Study type (predictive, empirical – if field collected data is utilised)
Codes context	– general	Plant major group (Angiosperm, Pteridophyta, Gymnosperm, Bryophyta, Multiple, (*Excluding Thallophyta)) No. of species in study (continuous data) Protected Area (yes, no, partial depending on study location in relation to Protected Areas, National Parks, or recognised Biodiversity Hotspots) Spatial Resolution (converted to km ²)
Codes - methods		Species Data (presence-only, presence/absence, site occupancy e.g., planned surveys including abundance, habitat suitability, land cover/vegetation types) Climate focus (past, present (including recent past e.g., back to 1950), future, multiple time focus) No. of climate scenarios (filtered only for climate focus: future) Future projection date (e.g., 2100) Model type/software (Ensemble, MaxEnt, Random Forest, Bayesian, Others) Model approach (Correlative, Mechanistic (Process-based), Combination) Range shift type (Geographical, Latitudinal, Elevational e.g., upslope/downslope, Multiple) Range shift measurement/metric (Habitat net change, Habitat direction, Rate of change, Habitat exposure, Spatial disruption, Multiple, Map comparison e.g., no quantitative data) Model parameters (Bioclimatic, Topographic, Edaphic, Lithological, Dispersal, Disturbance, Traits, LULCC, Physiological, Genetics) Overall range shift result (overall expansion, contraction, mix, stasis)
Retrospective codes		Range shift velocity (km/yr if stated) Biotic interactions e.g., dispersers (dynamic, static, none) Limitations (notes collected from individual articles about the limitations of the study) Practical application (understanding the impact of climate change, biodiversity conservation, assisted migration, invasion management)

6. Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge Neal Haddaway, a Research Fellow at the Stockholm Environment Institute who created the beta version of EviAtlas to bring our open-source, systematic map to life. This work was supported by a doctoral research studentship from Kingston University London, UK.

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Author biographies

PhD Candidate Emma Hall (corresponding author and main applicant) – EH

EH graduated with a BSc in GIS from Newcastle University and spent 8 years in the GIS profession before moving back to academia to research the best ways to model future range-shifts of plant species in response to climatic, land-use and land cover changes in Madagascar.

Associate Professor Kerry Brown (1st supervisor of EH) – KAB

KAB is a plant ecologist and conservation biologist. He received a BSc in Biology from Howard University, MSc and PhD from Stony Brook University and a postdoctoral fellowship at Columbia. His research integrates ecological data at multiple spatial scales to assess how environmental change impacts on biodiversity patterns/ecosystem function.

Professor Nigel Walford (2nd supervisor) – NW

NW studied Geography before gaining a PhD (University of London) where he worked on rural change. His research reflects a longstanding focus on quantitative analysis of geospatial data in relation to geodemographics, spatial planning, and environmental monitoring. NW has been funded by ESRC, Scottish Executive, Nuffield and the British Academy.

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MM's research interests include modelling land surface and ecological impacts of environmental change especially land-use change and climate change; desertification and land degradation in arid and semi arid environments; hydrological processes and impacts in Mediterranean and tropical environments with particular emphasis on vegetation hydrology interactions; tropical forest processes and dynamics.